

Juniper Pastures: Remnants of a Traditional an Agroforestry System

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Juniper is a light-loving tree that prefers stable habitat conditions

Common juniper (*Juniperus communis* L.) is a light-loving shrub or woody plant with multipurpose use, which used to be abundant mainly in pastures and meadows. Nowadays, it is often found only in difficult to access locations, or in nature reserves. It is associated to stable habitat conditions and is not an adaptable species that adapts to disturbed conditions. At the same time, it is classified as a vulnerable species with low reproductive capacity. Currently, its occurrence in Slovakia is significantly reduced. The way out of this unfavorable situation is the introduction of agroforestry systems in the management of permanent grasslands and the establishment of juniper pastures, where livestock grazing and fruit production would be combined. Vrchdetva in central Slovakia is one of the last places, where large-scale juniper stands can be found in Slovakia. In order for the common juniper to thrive in this area again, it is necessary to return grazing by livestock. To this end, it was first necessary to change the nature of the pastures and meadows, which are now mostly overgrown with trees and other shrubs. For this reason, the first step was to saw and mill selected junipers in the pastures. Later, the site was extensively grazed by approximately 500 sheep on an area of 26 ha. The aim of the cooperation between the National Forest Centre, the State Nature Conservancy of the Slovak Republic and a local farmer is to ensure that economic and conservation goals can be implemented simultaneously and thus ensure a favorable condition of juniper pastures and an increase in overall biodiversity in these locations.

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